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Research Article

**COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF VARIOUS ANIMAL TO
HUMAN TRANSMITTED HUMAN CORONAVIRUSES**¹Dr Ayesha Rehab, ²Dr Anam Nasim, ³Dr Zakir Jamal¹PMDC 101958-P, ²PMDC 101013-P, ³PMDC 29648-N

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Abstract:

Following the episode of the severe extreme respiratory disease on the earth, human Covid has been described as microorganisms that cause significant evidence of respiratory lot infection. Lately, another HCoV segregated from the respiratory epithelium of unidentified pneumonia patients on the Wuhan fish market induced a major disease episode and was referred to as the extreme severe respiratory syndrome of Covid 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Our current research was conducted at PIMS, Islamabad from February 2019 to October 2019. This infection triggers severe pulmonary symptoms, leading to a disease called "Covid infection 2019" (COVID-19). The rise of SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV induced boundless fear and worry and threatened the stability of the world's well-being. There are a few distinctions and contrasts in the disease transmission analysis and clinical highlights of these two infections, the diseases caused by these infections. The purpose of this work is to investigate and consider purposely between SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 with respect to their infection, initiation, conclusion and treatment methods, genomic and proteomic successions and pathogenic components.

Keywords: Comprehensive Evaluation, Animal-to-Human Transmitted, Human Coronaviruses.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Ayesha Rehab,**
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INTRODUCTION:

Covariates are a set of infections that co-contaminate people and other vertebrate creatures. CoV diseases influence the respiratory, gastrointestinal, hepatic and focal sensory systems of people, animals, poultry, bats, mice and many other wild creatures [1]. For example, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) in 2002 and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) in 2012 are two CoV diseases that have been transmitted from creatures to humans [2]. The source of unexplained pneumonia was first found in Wuhan in December 2019, and the SARS CoV-2, another Covid, was disengaged from the respiratory epithelium of patients. It has a place with another development branch inside the CoV. On February 11, 2019, the new Covid was officially renamed "SARS-CoV-2" from "2019-nCoV" [3]. The disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 was classified as "Covide 2019 infection" (Coronavirus) [7]. As reported by the National Health Commission of the People's Republic of China, SARS CoV-2 has most likely been transmitted from wild bats to humans, and all CoVs of more than three types can be transmitted from one individual to another [4]. The SARS-2 CoV offers a

quality device and standards of conduct that are profoundly comparable to those of the SARS CoV. This document summarizes the similarities and contrasts between CoV-2 and CoV, both of which cause significant disease episodes in China and worldwide, providing a comprehensive reference for plague control [5].

METHODOLOGY:

The amino corrosive groupings of 29 proteins in SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV were equivalent to the amino corrosive groups of 29 proteins by using GSPI Blastp. SARS and SARS-CoV-2 proteins were treated as homologous: personality esteem $\geq 67\%$, query inclusion $\geq 96\%$. Our current research was conducted at PIMS, Islamabad from February 2019 to October 2019. The comparative genomic investigations of SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV were carried out with a z-picture for a global analysis. A number of groupings and creation of phylogenetic trees of 38 CoVs were performed using MEGA7. Transformative distances were calculated using the Greatest Cumulative Probability technique.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

RESULTS:

Distinctions and similarities in clinical attributes between COVID-19 and SARS have been summarized in Table 1. On November 27, 2002, a respiratory illness broke out in Guangdong Province, China. In

February 2003, the Chinese Ministry of Health reported that this intense respiratory illness had so far resulted in 305 cases and five deaths. The following month, clusters of atypical pneumonia were identified in different parts of China, Hong Kong, Canada and

Singapore. By July 2003, SARS-CoV had spread to 28 countries on six continents and caused a total of 7,099 cases and 774 deaths (10.7%). Specifically, higher mortality (23%) was observed among medical clinic staff. On December 31, 2019, the Public Health Commission of the People's Republic of China and the Chinese Center for Disease Control (CDC China) began reviewing and studying cases through labor. On the same day, the Wuhan Public Authority provided

the company with data on disease episodes. Today, the number of patients with SARS-CoV-2 is rising worldwide. At the time of writing, a total of 68,082 cases and 1,528 deaths (4.3%) have been reported worldwide. In Wuhan, China, the number is 38,917. The basic timeline for improving the fight against SARS and the scourge of coronaviruses is shown in Figures 1a and 1b, separately.

Table 1:

4,14,16,18-24

Compared to SARS-CoV^{18,23,25-27} and MERS-CoV^{12,14,18,25,28}

	SARS-CoV	MERS-CoV	SARS-CoV-2
Epidemiology			
Date of outbreak	November 2002	June 2012	December 2019
Disease	SARS	MERS	COVID-19
Origin	China	Saudi Arabia	Wuhan, China
Region covered	29 countries	28 countries	Worldwide
Confirmed cases	8096	2494	>21 million
Death toll	774	858	>700,000
Inflammatory cytokines			
IL-6	↑	↑	↑
IL-17	Unknown	↑	↑
IL-1	ns	ns	↑
TNF α	↑	↑	↑
MCPI	↑	Unknown	↑
CRP	↑	↑	↑

Abbreviations: SARS-CoV, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus; MERS, Middle East respiratory syndrome; SARS-CoV-2, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2; IL, interleukin; TNF α , tumor necrosis factor- α ; MCP1, monocyte chemoattractant protein-1; CRP, C-reactive protein; ns, not significant; ↑, increase.

Table 2:**Table 2.** Comparison of protein sequences SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV by Blastp.

SARS-CoV-2			SARS-CoV			
Protein Name	Accession Number	Putative Function/Domain	Accession Number	Query Cover *	Percent Identity	
1	nsp2	YP_009725298.1	nonstructural polyprotein pp1a	ABF65834.1	100%	68.34%
2	nsp3	YP_009725299.1	polyprotein orf1a	AFR58698.1	100%	75.82%
3	nsp4	YP_009725300.1	polyprotein 1a	ARO76381.1	100%	80.80%
4	nsp6	YP_009725302.1	nsp6-pp1a/pp1ab (TM3)	NP_828864.1	98%	88.15%
5	nsp7	YP_009725303.1	Chain A, Replicase Polyprotein 1ab, Light Chain	2AHM_A	100%	98.80%
6	nsp8	YP_009725304.1	Chain E, Replicase Polyprotein 1ab, Heavy Chain	2AHM_E	100%	97.47%
7	nsp9	YP_009725305.1	nsp9-pp1a/pp1ab	NP_828867.1	100%	97.35%
8	nsp10	YP_009725306.1	Chain A, Non-structural Protein 10	5C8S_A	100%	97.12%
9	nsp11	YP_009725312.1	nsp11-pp1a	NP_904321.1	100%	84.62%
10	orf1a polyprotein	YP_009725295.1	orf1a polyprotein (pp1a)	NP_828850.1	100%	80.58%
11	orf1ab polyprotein	YP_009724389.1	orf1ab polyprotein (pp1ab)	NP_828849.2	100%	86.26%
12	orf3a protein	YP_009724391.1	hypothetical protein sars3a	NP_828852.2	100%	72.04%
13	orf6 protein	YP_009724394.1	hypothetical protein sars6	NP_828856.1	100%	68.85%
14	orf7a protein	YP_009724395.1	protein 8	ARO76387.1	100%	87.70%
15	orf7b protein	YP_009725296.1	hypothetical protein sars7b	NP_849175.1	95%	85.37%
16	orf8 protein	YP_009724396.1	-	-	-	-
17	orf10 protein	YP_009725255.1	-	-	-	-
18	2'-O-ribose methyltransferase	YP_009725311.1	nsp16-pp1ab (2'-o-MT)	NP_828873.2	99%	93.60%
19	3C-like proteinase	YP_009725301.1	polyprotein 1a	ARO76381.1	100%	96.08%
20	3'-to-5' exonuclease	YP_009725309.1	nsp14-pp1ab (nuclease ExoN homolog)	NP_828871.1	100%	95.07%
21	endoRNase	YP_009725310.1	nsp15-pp1ab (endoRNase)	NP_828872.1	100%	88.73%
22	envelope protein	YP_009724392.1	E protein	AP040581.1	100%	94.74%
23	helicase	YP_009725308.1	nsp13-pp1ab (ZD, NTPase/HEL)	NP_828870.1	100%	99.83%
24	leader protein	YP_009725297.1	nsp1-pp1a/pp1ab	NP_828860.2	100%	84.44%
25	membrane glycoprotein	YP_009724393.1	matrix protein	NP_828855.1	100%	90.54%
26	nucleocapsid phosphoprotein	YP_009724397.2	nucleocapsid protein	ARO76389.1	100%	90.52%
27	RNA-dependent RNA polymerase	YP_009725307.1	nsp12-pp1ab (RdRp)	NP_828869.1	100%	96.35%
28	surface glycoprotein	YP_009724390.1	spike glycoprotein	ABD72985.1	100%	76.42%

"-" represents no homologous protein. Query cover represents the percentage of the protein sequences that are participating in the comparison. Percent identity indicates the homology.

DISCUSSION:

As an enormous number of individuals have left Wuhan, control of the circumstances of the pestilence is surprisingly serious, and COVID-19 medications are inevitable [6]. On February 14, 2019, there were more than 54,000 patients reported in Hubei territory, China. Due to the lack of viable antiviral drugs, the patients' visualization is based exclusively on their age and health status. Despite the fact that it has been revealed that the number of clinically recovered patients exceeds the number of deaths, most patients are still not relieved in emergency clinics [7]. In addition, the expected multifaceted transformation of SARS-CoV-2 makes it difficult to advance vaccination [8]. There is therefore an urgent need to develop more sensitive investigation techniques and effective drugs. Seven types of CoV have been identified to cause human infection. The two deeply pathogenic infections, CoV-SAR and CoV-MERS, cause serious respiratory problems in humans [9]. The other four human CoVs (HCoV-NL63, HCoV-229E, HCoV-OC43 and HKU1) cause only upper respiratory tract disease, while some of them can cause severe illness in infants, young children and the elderly. The most recent is SARS-CoV-2. It was explained that SARS-CoV-2 shared almost 80% of the genome with SARS-CoV. Our results also showed that the virtually fully encoded proteins of CoV-2 are homologous to the proteins of SARS-CoV (Table 2). Subsequently, drugs and clinical treatments for the treatment of SARS could be used as a kind of perspective for COVID-19 treatment [10].

CONCLUSION:

Since a growing number of studies for SARS-CoV-2 have appeared since the episode of this scourge of COVID-19, in the light of our correlation, we suggest some critical investigations to be clarified in future investigations (Table 3). Top to bottom understanding of the essential pathogenic systems of SARS-CoV-2 will reveal more emphasis on improved management of COVID-19.

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